

Particles and Vacuum as Strings from the Quantum of Action

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Reviving atomism in its most fundamental form, we take the quantum of action h as the basic building block of particles and the vacuum, as empirical evidence dictates. In its simplest form, the quantum of light under U(1) gauge symmetry spans space by its wavelength and time by its period. In its circular, planar form of SU(2) symmetry, \hbar corresponds to the electron neutrino. Twisted once along its path, this quantum loop becomes the muon neutrino, and twice, the more curved, hence more massive, tau neutrino. The fine-structure constant defines the electron of SU(2)_L chiral symmetry as a toroidal string of quanta, and the positron of SU(2)_R as its antiparticle. Shedding a neutrino loop, the torus opens to a W boson. The toroidal fractions $1/3$ and $2/3$ correspond to quarks or antiquarks by fractional charges, and to the 1st, 2nd, and 3rd generations by twisting number. Three quarks on three tetrahedral faces close via gluon-like quanta to a baryon exhibiting SU(3) symmetry and charge in multiples of e due to 2π flux quantization. A honeycomb packing of nucleons accounts for nuclear shape and stability. In reactions, toroidal arcs of quanta with opposite chirality annihilate into collinear rays of photons with opposite phases; these constitute a transparent, massless, quantized, and relativistic vacuum. As the quanta of matter transform into the quanta of space through astrophysical processes, the universe expands from a dense past to an ever sparser present toward the thermodynamic balance of heat death.

I. INTRODUCTION

What is everything made of? The age-old question seeks fundamental substance. However, the ancient atomistic ideal of an indivisible, indestructible element seems too reductive to account for the many particles currently classified as elementary. While the Standard Model (SM) demonstrates remarkable empirical alignment, it remains an effective theory that leaves fundamental questions open. Specifically, it struggles to explain why nature presents the specific particles it does, what dictates the hierarchy of forces between them, what caused the matter-antimatter asymmetry, what sets the arrow of time, why quarks carry $\pm 1/3$ and $\pm 2/3$ of the electric charge, how neutrinos acquire mass, what causes charge-parity (CP) violation, what constitutes dark matter, and what underlies dark energy or vacuum energy [1–4].

What if these profound problems point to foundations that are too flexible rather than too complex? Rationalizing the SM begins with discerning that the strict stoichiometry of particle reactions implies common constituents—much as the stoichiometry of chemical reactions once suggested shared subatomic components, rationalizing the periodic table. Because all known particles and the vacuum transform into one another through reactions, they must logically assemble from the same fundamental element.

Since every particle and its antiparticle ultimately resolve into photons that undergo no further decay, the light quantum emerges as the prime candidate for this common constituent. We examine how this basic building block—the quantum of action that measures the invariant h —can account for the three fermion generations and the five force-carrying bosons, while also embodying the spatial substance of both electromagnetic and gravitational fields.

Historically, Newton’s query as to whether light and matter are fundamentally commensurate [5] prefigured the search for an elemental entity. Crystallizing the insights of Planck and Einstein, Lewis rephrased this ancient atomism by naming the light quantum the photon [6]—an insight that remains as irrefutable as it is ignored.

Despite its logical appeal, this material monism gave way to particle pluralism born of practical problems. For example, researchers reasoned that “if the electron is a composite particle, its constituents are strongly bound, giving the electron the observed point-like quality at experimentally accessible energies” [7]. Although high-energy collisions have yet to break electrons or quarks, the stoichiometry of electron capture, beta decay, pair production, and annihilation implies that leptons, hadrons, and the vacuum itself must share a common constituent. How else could such transformations occur if they were not rearrangements of basic building blocks?

As the ironclad logic of fundamental unity fell out of favor, Quantum Field Theory (QFT) came into focus. In the QFT framework, particles are interpreted as excitations of their respective fields: mass arises from coupling to the gravitational field and charge arises from interactions with the electromagnetic field. However, rather than populating

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the vacuum with multiple independent fields, observations can be understood as particles perturbing a single spatial substance into orthogonal fields.

As envisioned by Faraday and Einstein, variations in the density of this all-permeating physical vacuum manifest themselves as gravitational fields, while gradients in its phase manifest themselves as electromagnetic fields [8–10]. Consequently, what appear to be inexplicable attraction and repulsion between particles reveal themselves as manifestations of particles being carried by space in flux toward the thermodynamic balance of least action, a state corresponding to the minimal curvature and torsion of the spatial substance [11–13].

From this perspective, the quantum of action has not been disproven; rather, it has been disregarded as the basic building block. Unlike hypothetical preons, geons, or partons, the massless photon stands as an indivisible and indestructible entity that embodies Planck’s constant $h = Et$, the quantum of action having energy E over its period t . Thus, while virtual photons serve as a mathematical means for calculating interactions, we identify both particles and the vacuum as composed of physical quanta. These are light-like strings of action whose specific geometries give rise to the observed properties of particles and their fields [14].

Paradoxically, given how few photons emerge from annihilation events, the quantum of action as the basic building block may seem unconvincing. The resolution lies in phase: when paired in opposite phases, the individual electromagnetic fields of the light quanta cancel, rendering the resulting bosonic substance transparent to radiation. A pair of photons as a massless spin-2 particle embodies the unit of spatial substance, the graviton. Consequently, photons do not propagate through the vacuum; they constitute it. This *light-comprising*, yet transparent, relativistic substance, undulating with wave speed c , naturally accounts for the null results of classical experiments designed to detect a *light-carrying* luminiferous aether.

Conceptualizing photons not only as force carriers, but as the elemental substance threading both particles and the vacuum underscores that observations are inherently theory-laden [15]. This paradigm shift reveals charge–parity–time (CPT) symmetry as an intrinsic property of a chiral string: charge conjugation reverses its handedness; parity inverts its spatial coordinates; and time reversal flips its propagation direction. Accordingly, rather than attributing hidden colors to a gluon gauge boson, a short-wavelength photon with its propagation direction explicitly connects a preceding quark to a succeeding one, binding them into composite particles, naturally conforming to their respective quantum statistics. Similarly, rather than relying on color neutrality as a standalone postulate, vacuum flux quantization acts as a constituent principle, naturally constraining quarks into unit-charge combinations.

In what follows, we proceed to describe the vacuum and particles as structured strings of quanta, in a manner consistent with empirical data, and thereby concretizing, rather than contradicting, the Standard Model. This approach is motivated by the fact that the proposed atomistic axiom is foundational and directly falsifiable by evidence to the contrary, such as detecting a photon splitting or decaying.

II. THE VACUUM AS RAYS OF QUANTA

In 1865, Maxwell derived his equations by conceptualizing space as a fluid of light, undulating with a wave speed $c^2 = 1/\varepsilon_0\mu_0$, determined by permittivity ε_0 and permeability μ_0 [16–18]. Equivalently, $c^2 = GM/R$ is determined by the gravitational potential of the universe, characterized by its total mass M and its expanding causal radius $R = ct$ [19].

Despite sharing the common wave speed, the long-sought unification of gravitation, as an intrinsic property of space, and electromagnetism, as its configurational property [8, 9], never materialized as a physical substance. Instead, the geometrization of gravitation as spacetime curvature effectively dematerialized space and detached electromagnetism from it [20]. This theoretical distancing from physical space once arose from confounding observations, which, through conceptual reorientation, now become entirely comprehensible.

Crucially, the Michelson–Morley experiment ruled out a *light-carrying* medium, but not a *light-comprising* space in which light rays are paired with opposite phases (Fig. 1) [21]. The interferometric null result merely demonstrated the presence of an isotropic spatial substance characterized by a wave speed c [18]. As observed in the Fizeau experiment, a phase shift emerges only when the excess density of the spatial substance within a moving medium is entrained. In turn, stellar aberration and the Sagnac experiment are independent of the refractive index, not because there is no spatial substance, but because n cancels out in the ratio $c_x/n \div c_y/n$ of the wave speed components tangential and orthogonal to the detector’s velocity.

Photon pairs constitute a transparent, relativistic, and Lorentz-invariant vacuum that conforms to Planck’s law of radiation, a distribution derived from Bose–Einstein statistics with two polarization states per photon [10, 22]. Thermal excitation dissociates these pairs into detectable radiation, while they recombine as the temperature drops. The vacuum of paired photons is also consistent with the dynamic Casimir effect, which explicitly extracts two photons at a time from the vacuum [23].

As an integral constituent of the vacuum, the photon does not couple to it, consistent with a massless, stable

FIG. 1. When a ray of light (above) pairs with an out-of-phase ray (below), their oscillating electric and magnetic fields cancel. Yet the paired photons themselves persist as the transparent elements of the vacuum. (Illustration by Mathematica)

ground state [24]. Furthermore, this paired-photon vacuum is inherently free of spatial and temporal singularities because the photon, measuring $h = Et = \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{x}$, physically embodies a spatial dimension through its wavelength \mathbf{x} and a temporal dimension through its period t [25]. Rephrasing Fermat's principle, light quanta make, rather than take, the least-time paths along the steepest gradients in energy, the lines of force, the null geodesics through spacetime [26, 27]. This interpretation of the vacuum as strings of action that carry energy E over time t and momentum \mathbf{p} along wavelength \mathbf{x} parallels the phase-space action integral.

A. Variations in vacuum density

Shifting the perspective from photons *moving* through a vacuum to photons *making* the vacuum redefines the nature of light propagation. In this view, the speed of light $c = \lambda/\tau$ is an intrinsic property of the spatial substance, an invariant independent of the wavelength λ and the period τ , yet a variable dependent on the vacuum density.

A local gravitational potential $\phi_o = GM_o/r$ expresses the vacuum density at a distance r from a mass M_o , through the gravitational refractive index [28],

$$n^2 = \frac{c^2}{c'^2} = \frac{1}{1 - GM_o/c^2 r} = \frac{1}{1 - M_o R/Mr} = \frac{f_e}{f_o} = 1 + z, \quad (1)$$

relative to the universal potential $\phi = GM/R = c^2$ generated by the total mass M within the causal radius R . The reduced speed c' manifests itself as the gravitational redshift z between the emitted frequency f_e and the observed frequency f_o .

A local angular acceleration $\alpha = GM_o/r^3$ bends a ray that originates and is observed far from M_o by $\theta = 1/2\alpha t^2 = 4\pi^2 GM_o/2c^2 r$, resulting in a delay of $\Delta t \approx r\theta/c = 2\pi^2 GM_o/c^3$ [10, 29]. In contrast, General Relativity (GR) uses two disparate formulas $\theta_{GR} \approx 4GM_o/c^2 r$ and $\Delta t_{GR} \approx 2GM_o/c^3 [\ln(4r_E r_P/r^2) - 1]$ for the same photon propagation. Nevertheless, the GR-calculated effects for the Sun [30] match measurements when the displacement of parallel rays is neglected [29, 31] and when the logarithmic factor in square brackets is approximately π^2 , as is the case for the Earth–Sun distance r_E and the Venus–Sun distance r_P .

Similarly, the global decrease in vacuum density—from the dense early universe of mass M_e and radius $R_e = c_e t_e$ at the time of emission t_e to the sparse present when the photon is detected—causes a cosmological redshift z ,

$$n^2 = \frac{c^2}{c_e^2} = \frac{1}{1 - GM_e/c^2 R_e} = \frac{1}{1 - M_e R/MR_e} = \frac{f_e}{f_o} = 1 + z. \quad (2)$$

In this view, the photon climbs the cosmic gravity well exactly as it climbs from the local gravitational potentials of stars, galaxies, or clusters into the sparser surrounding space. Consequently, this density gradient across the expanding universe provides a physical account of the Type Ia supernovae data without invoking dark energy [10, 29].

As matter transforms into space via elementary particle reactions in stars, pulsars, quasars, and other astrophysical processes [10, 29, 32, 33], the spatial and temporal variations of the gravitational potential, embodied in the paired-photon substance, originate equally from the density of matter ρ_M ,

$$\nabla^2\phi(\mathbf{r}, t) \equiv \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \phi(\mathbf{r}, t) \equiv 4\pi G \rho_M(\mathbf{r}, t). \quad (3)$$

This mass-energy-gravity equivalence,

$$Mc^2 = GM^2/R \Rightarrow 4\pi G \rho_M = \frac{c^2}{R^2} = \frac{1}{t^2} = -\frac{dH}{dt}, \quad (4)$$

describes matter transforming into expanding physical space at a decelerating rate, $dH/dt = -1/t^2$, rather than an abstract metric stretching at an accelerating rate without cause.

As envisioned early on [34, 35], this conservation of quanta during stoichiometric matter-to-space transformations equates $\rho_M \approx 6 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ with the critical density $\rho_c = 1/4\pi G t^2$. As ρ_c decreases over time t , the universe remains naturally flat, leaving no room for fine-tuning the cosmological constant $\Lambda \equiv 1/R^2$. Accordingly, the pressure of expansion $p = \rho_c c^2 = c^2/4\pi G t^2$ derives from matter transforming into spatial substance rather than dark energy—a parameter introduced to reconcile the parametric scaling $1+z = a(t)/a(t_e)$ with empirical data.

According to Gauss's flux theorem,

$$\Phi_R = \int \mathbf{a}_R \cdot d\mathbf{S}_R = -4\pi G \int \rho_M dV = -4\pi G M, \quad (5)$$

all matter of mass M , transforming into space, puts space itself in flux through the expanding surface $S = 4\pi R^2$. As in hydrodynamics, the efflux into sparser surroundings draws bodies together, resulting in local attraction, including threshold acceleration $a_R = GM/R^2 = c/t \approx 10^{-10} \text{ ms}^{-2}$, as inferred from galaxy rotation curves and velocity dispersions [36–42]. Conversely, the influx from matter-to-space transformations drives bodies apart, resulting in cosmic expansion. This understanding of gravity as space in flux leaves no role for dark matter, modified Newtonian dynamics (MOND), or dark energy [10, 13].

As the vacuum energy density ρ decreases with cosmic expansion, the flux-balance radius $r_{ta}^3 = GM_o t^2$ increases over time t . Consequently, structures spontaneously form on ever larger scales, much earlier than predicted by the Λ CDM model [43]. In turn, the least dense regions, such as the Local Hole, naturally characterize the present era.

Although the threshold acceleration a_R is only about $10^{-11}g$, far too low to detect on the Earth's surface, the corresponding field $-(\phi/c^2)\partial\mathbf{v}/\partial t$ induced by a change in velocity \mathbf{v} relative to the universal potential ϕ is readily experienced as inertia [44]. Following Mach's insight, the r^2 increase in the number of galaxies outnumbers the $1/r$ decrease in their individual potentials, resulting in flat, featureless, and far-extending background acceleration $\mathbf{a}_R = -\nabla\phi$, consistent with Birkhoff's theorem and the cosmological principle.

Gravitational and inertial masses are identical because all bodies are coupled to the same spatial substance that embodies both local and universal gravitational potentials. As Einstein realized, a body in free fall does not experience gravity because it is coupled to space in free flux. Accordingly, when the influx and efflux of space tally, the orbit remains stationary: the orbiter sweeps out equal areas in equal times, gaining as much spatial substance by advancing tangentially as it displaces by falling radially.

Furthermore, the precession of the apsides reveals that the kinetic energy balances not only the local potential but also the universal potential, $\phi = c^2 = GM/R$, due to all matter [45]. As quantified by GR, all local phenomena are relative to this universal background, manifested in the CMB dipole.

B. Gradients in the vacuum phase

As the double-slit experiment demonstrates, a photon, an electron, or any other particle generates waves in the physical vacuum, which can subsequently interfere with the particle itself. Consequently, a particle's motion and its driving forces are fundamentally inseparable, precluding a definitive solution to the equation of motion. This non-determinism is conceptually distinct from both the probabilistic indeterminism of the Copenhagen interpretation and the strictly determined trajectories of pilot-wave theory [27, 46].

The Aharonov-Bohm variant of the double-slit experiment demonstrates that a phase shift $\varphi = e/\hbar \int V dt$ develops as a charged particle moves through an electric scalar potential V over time t . Similarly, $\varphi = e/\hbar \int \mathbf{A} \cdot d\mathbf{x}$ develops as the particle traverses a magnetic vector potential \mathbf{A} along a path \mathbf{x} . Furthermore, the optical effects of Faraday

and Kerr show that the divergence and curl of the spatial substance affect photon polarization (Fig. 1). In this view, the Lorenz gauge,

$$\nabla V + \frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + c \nabla \cdot \mathbf{A} = 0, \quad (6)$$

emerges as a statement of vacuum continuity, where a spatial change in the scalar potential V is balanced by a temporal change in the vector potential \mathbf{A} or vice versa.

Consequently, a charge e moving with velocity \mathbf{v} is not attracted or repelled through inexplicable action-at-a-distance; instead, it moves coupled to a vacuum of paired rays whose torsion diverges from charges as the electric field \mathbf{E} and whose phase curls around currents as the magnetic field \mathbf{B} , as described by the Lorentz force,

$$\mathbf{F} = e(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}). \quad (7)$$

Moreover, as Bohr originally conjectured and experiments with superconducting loops later confirmed, the physical vacuum within a closed surface S constrains the phase of any stationary state to 2π multiples, $\Delta\varphi = (e/\hbar) \oint \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = 2\pi n$, rather than this being an intrinsic property of the charge carrier.

With these insights into fields as manifestations of variations in the density and phase of the physical vacuum, we now turn to the sources of the fields: the particles themselves.

III. PARTICLES AS STRINGS OF QUANTA

A string comprising n elemental actions h integrates into a discrete quantized action,

$$nh = \int E dt = \int \mathbf{p} \cdot d\mathbf{x}, \quad (8)$$

which carries energy E over the period t , or, equivalently, momentum \mathbf{p} over the wavelength \mathbf{x} [47]. In this view, a particle is an invariant action characterized by conserved energy and time that contrasts with the stretching and twisting rays of vacuum quanta that constitute gravitational and electromagnetic fields.

By breaking the gauge symmetry of the vacuum, the particle is the source of the gravitational field \mathbf{a} enclosed by a surface \mathbf{S} , where the vacuum rays curve in proportion to the mass $m = -\int \mathbf{a} \cdot d\mathbf{S}/4\pi G$. Similarly, an electric charge $q = \varepsilon_0 \int \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}$ is the source of the electric field \mathbf{E} , where the phases of the paired rays diverge, while a magnetic moment $\mu = IS$, curls them in proportion to the current $I = \int (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot d\mathbf{S}/\mu_0$ per Ampère's law. In this way, the mass m , the charge q , and the magnetic moment μ derive respectively from the curvature, winding, and curl of the invariant action—the particle itself.

Specifically, mass is proportional to the total curvature, as expressed by the Euler characteristic of the Gauss-Bonnet theorem,

$$2\pi\chi = \int_{n\gamma} k_g d\gamma + \int K dS = \mathbf{n} \cdot \int_{n\gamma} \mathbf{k} d\gamma + \int K dS = \mathbf{n} \cdot \int_{n\gamma} \frac{\gamma'' \times \gamma'}{|\gamma'|^3} d\gamma + \int K dS, \quad (9)$$

where the geodesic curvature k_g is integrated along a string of n quanta following a specific path γ , expressed in terms of the tangent γ' (velocity) and the curvature vector γ'' (acceleration), and $K = 1/R^2$ denotes the minute Gaussian curvature of the universal vacuum, a nearly flat background reference characterized by the immense causal radius R and a bounding surface $S = 4\pi R^2$, with unit normal \mathbf{n} .

By the same topological logic, the electric charge is proportional to the number of windings w per length of the string $\sigma = w/n\gamma$,

$$q = \frac{e}{w_e} \int_{n\gamma} \sigma d\gamma, \quad (10)$$

normalized by the characteristic winding number w_e of the unit charge e .

Finally, the magnetic moment is proportional to the curl along the string path γ ,

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \int \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{j} dV = \frac{1}{2} I \oint_{n\gamma} \mathbf{r} \times d\gamma, \quad (11)$$

where the constituent quanta carry the current $\mathbf{I} = \int \mathbf{j} dV$, generating the intrinsic angular momentum or spin.

The following sections describe Standard Model particles—forming spin-1/2 and spin-3/2 baryons, pseudoscalar and vector mesons, and exotic mesons—and their corresponding stoichiometric reactions, best examined interactively using the Colab notebook `ParticlesFromPhotons.ipynb`, also available on [GitHub](#). Strings can also be constructed using the `CurveGraphics` `Mathematica` package.

A. Leptons

As their name suggests, leptons correspond to strings with low geodesic curvature, as simple loops or shallow-pitch tori.

1. Neutrino

The neutrino ν , which has spin but lacks both charge and magnetic moment, corresponds under SU(2) symmetry to a single quantum loop of action \hbar (Fig. 2). Its antiparticle, the antineutrino $\bar{\nu}$, is the reverse circulation. As the Dirac belt trick demonstrates, the vacuum's paired-photon ray, when coupled to such a spin-1/2 particle, returns to its initial state only after a 4π rotation.

The mass of the planar electron neutrino ν_e is non-zero as a consequence of the non-vanishing background curvature (Eq. (9)). This minute mass manifests the subtle deviation of the universe from exact flatness, resulting from its enormous but finite causal radius R . The muon neutrino circulation is twisted by 2π ; consequently, as much as ν_μ bends out of the plane, its geodesic curvature and thus its mass are greater than those of ν_e . The doubly-twisted tau neutrino ν_τ is even more curved. Via the Mikheyev-Smirnov-Wolfenstein effect, neutrinos oscillate between these generations to maintain thermodynamic balance with the surrounding curvature. By extension, even a triply twisted neutrino might manifest under extreme energy densities.

FIG. 2. The electron neutrino is a planar, single-quantum circulation; its antineutrino is the reverse-sense circulation.

2. Electron

As Ampère, Parson, and Compton envisioned [48], the electron e^- of SU(2)_L symmetry, having charge, magnetic moment, and mass, is a toroidal string (Fig. 3). Its discrete number of quanta can be deduced from the fine-structure constant, interpreted as a ratio of actions,

$$\alpha = \frac{L}{\hbar} = \int \frac{2Kdt}{\hbar} = \frac{\int Udt}{\hbar} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 c \hbar} \frac{1}{\hbar} = \frac{e^2 Z_o}{2\hbar}, \quad (12)$$

where the electron action $L = 2Kt = Ut$ integrates the intrinsic kinetic energy $2K$ in balance with the potential $U = e^2/4\pi\epsilon_0 r$ over the period of circulation t within the vacuum of impedance Z_o . This action spans the number of windings $w = \int \sigma d\gamma$ along its toroidal chiral path γ of n quanta totaling the unit charge e . For $w = 137$ windings with the radius ratio $r/r_l = \pi$, the length of the torus $l = 2\pi r_l w(1 + [(r/r_l)/w]^2)^{1/2}$ per loop $2\pi r_l$ is equal to $1/\alpha \approx 137.036$. Due to this shallow pitch, each toroidal loop is only slightly longer than the planar loop quantum \hbar ; consequently, the toroidal path closes only with $n = 138$ quanta.

The unit charge e is consistent with the 2π modular phase φ of the magnetic flux quantum $\Phi_B = h/e = \hbar/e \oint \nabla\varphi \cdot d\mathbf{l} = \int \mathbf{B} \cdot d\mathbf{S} = eZ_o/2\alpha$ and the electric flux quantum $\Phi_E/c = \int \mathbf{E} \cdot d\mathbf{S}/c = eZ_o/2\alpha$. The vacuum impedance $Z_o = \sqrt{\mu_o/\epsilon_o}$, the intrinsic resistance of its paired-photon rays to twist and curl, is matched to the unit charge e through the identity $h = e^2 Z_o/2\alpha$. Consequently, fractional charges are unstable because they fail to satisfy the 2π periodicity for topological closure.

The magnetic moment $\mu_e = 1/2 I \oint \mathbf{r} \times d\mathbf{l} \approx \mu_B(1 + \alpha/2\pi)$, with the Bohr magneton $\mu_B = e\hbar/2m_e$, models the circulation as flowing along the major perimeter $2\pi r$, while summing secondary loops along the minor perimeter $2\pi r_l$. The anomalous part $\mu_B\alpha/2\pi$ corrects for the current $I = e/t$ over the Zitterbewegung period $t = (\hbar/m_e c^2)/(2\pi/\alpha)$ along the actual path l , where the toroidal components add, while the poloidal components cancel [14, 49].

The positron e^+ is the electron's antiparticle, characterized by opposite handedness. Upon annihilation, these right- and left-handed tori open; the strings uncoil and pair with opposite phases, integrating into the rays of the vacuum (Fig. 4). To compensate for the lost curvature, two photons of energy $E = m_e c^2$ are emitted in opposite directions, conserving momentum.

The electron mass $m_e = 9.11 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg} = 0.511 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ is small because, along its rising chiral path, any two constituent loops, i and j , on opposite sides are out of phase by $\varphi_{ij} = \pi$ and nearly antiparallel $\theta_{ij} \approx \pi$. Consequently, their signed curvatures almost cancel, leaving only the residual curvature of the helical pitch. In contrast, a single quantum i lacking such a symmetric counterpart j would yield a mass of $m_1 = 137m_e/138\alpha \approx 70 \text{ MeV}/c^2$.

In the 1950s, a characteristic mass unit approximately equal to m_1 was inferred from newly discovered particles, suggesting a fundamental periodicity analogous to the atomic mass unit [50, 51]. However, as many more particles were found, such simple systematics broke down. Although mass is observed as a scalar quantity, the total geodesic curvature of a string is not a simple scalar sum of its substrings curvatures (Eq. (9)). Instead, the mass resulting from two connected toroidal arcs can be modeled

FIG. 3. The electron (left) is a string of 138 quanta coiled into 137 loops. The positron torus (right) coils oppositely. The electron mass m_e accrues from the small net curvature along the pitch, manifesting as a lagging phase in the arrow heads.

FIG. 4. Electron and positron (left) annihilate by opening (middle) and unwinding pairwise to rays paired with opposite phases (right), becoming part of the vacuum.

as a pairwise summation

$$m = m_1 \sum_{i,j} [(1 - \cos^2 \theta_{ij}) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - \cos(\varphi_{ij} - \pi))] \quad (13)$$

over the dihedral angles $\cos \theta_{ij} = \mathbf{k}_i \cdot \mathbf{k}_j$ of loop curvature vectors and their phase differences φ_{ij} , scaled by m_1 .

In summary, the electron mass measures the coupling to the vacuum in terms of the total toroidal curvature, inherent in $SU(2)$ symmetry, while the electron charge and moment measure the coupling to the vacuum in terms of the total toroidal winding and net helical circulation inherent in $SU(2)_L$ chiral symmetry [52].

The electron torus $e^- \rightarrow W^- + \nu_e$ opens by shedding one of its loop quanta ν_e to become the W^- boson. The tight coupling of vacuum rays to the narrow one-loop slit manifests itself in $m_W = 80.4 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ (Fig. 5). This concrete restructuring of strings exemplifies the abstract exchange of force carriers in leptonic and hadronic transitions.

The muon μ^- structurally resembles e^- , except for its twisted loops that increase the total geodesic curvature, making m_μ significantly larger than m_e . The doubly-twisted tau is still heavier. Since this twist slightly shortens the loop radius r_l , the muon magnetic moment anomaly a_μ is slightly larger than a_e [53, 54]. In this view, the three generations are not disparate species but increasingly curved configurations of the same fundamental action.

A muon decays through $\mu^- \rightarrow W^- + \nu_\mu \rightarrow W^- + \nu_e \rightarrow e^-$, where the twisted torus opens and sheds one of its neutrino loops ν_μ . The resulting open torus W^- untwists, regains ν_e , and closes to form e^- . Accordingly, in high-energy collisions e^-e^+ , the opened tori W^- and W^+ may thread together, forming the Z boson (Fig. 6). This massive intermediate subsequently dissociates into $\mu^- \mu^+$ or even $\tau^- \tau^+$ pairs by absorbing the corresponding neutrino loops, depending on what it takes to balance the energy of the collision. The Z boson may also decay through hadronic channels.

FIG. 5. The electron (left) transforms into the W^- boson (right) by losing one loop, the neutrino.

FIG. 6. The string of quanta seamlessly threading through W^- and W^+ forms the Z boson. It is its own antiparticle. The arrows show the string direction.

B. Baryons

Baryons, comprising three quarks or three antiquarks, correspond to strings of quantized action winding through three toroidal arcs positioned on the faces of a tetrahedron, in accordance with $SU(3)$ symmetry. Short-wavelength quanta γ (gluons), the carriers of the strong force, link these arcs pairwise across the tetrahedral edges (Fig. 7). The down quark d is a $1/3$ fragment of e^- , while the up quark u is a $2/3$ fragment of e^+ . Higher-generation quarks are similar fractions of muon and tau tori, with antiquarks as their respective antiparticles.

The tetrahedral geometry is naturally associated with the eight-parameter special unitary group $SU(3)$, which defines the toroidal fragments by their handedness, lengths, positions, and relative phases, in conjunction with the three Euler angles that orient the tetrahedral frame. Subject to the topological requirement for the 2π closure, this representation is consistent with QCD. The oriented string itself embodies the antisymmetric quark ordering that QCD encodes as color. While QCD imposes color neutrality as a standalone postulate to confine quarks in stable states—characterized by well-defined angular momentum, invariant volume, and 2π -modular phase—free quarks are inherently unstable because their open strings accrue a phase incompatible with the 2π periodicity of the surrounding vacuum. For the same reason, baryons cannot comprise mixed quark-antiquark triplets.

1. Nucleons

The properties of the proton (uud) and neutron (ddu) derive from their respective tetrahedral structures (Fig. 7). The bulk of the nucleon mass, approximately $3 \times 312.5 = 937.5 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, results from the incomplete pairwise cancellation of the geodesic curvatures as the constituent arcs depart from the gluon vertices with a half-loop offset $\theta_o = \pi/138$ from the parallel alignment (Eq. (13)). Although u , comprising 92 quanta, is twice the length of d , comprising 46 quanta, both contribute nearly equally to the nucleon mass, because the curvatures of the additional loop quanta in the u arc almost completely cancel pairwise, generating a residual mass of only $1/3m_e$. The slight difference between $m_p = 938.3$ and $m_n = 939.6 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ may stem from

minor deviations from the ideal tetrahedral symmetry, potentially induced by electromagnetic self-energies.

FIG. 7. The proton (left) and neutron (right) are composed of quarks, arcs of tori, coordinated on three faces of a tetrahedron. The down quark (blue) is $1/3$ of the electron torus, and the up quark (red) is $2/3$ of the positron torus (outlined with gray circles). Gluons (black) as short-wavelength quanta connect the quarks across tetrahedron edges. A nucleon magnetic moment sums the quark moments (straight arrows), scaled by the flux through their areas of circulation (curved arrows). The proton and neutron structures are complementary to fit the same tetrahedron with effective three-fold symmetry, suggesting honeycomb nucleon packing.

Magnetic moments μ_p and μ_n are derived from string geometries in a manner analogous to the calculation of an electric current loop via Stokes' theorem. Summing the moments of the constituent quarks yields a ratio of $\mu_p/\mu_n = -1.35$, which deviates by about 8% from the measured -1.46 . This discrepancy is likely due to subtle deviations from the ideal tetrahedral symmetry (Fig. 7). Furthermore, the neutron does not exhibit an electric dipole moment because its fractional charges are not discrete entities, but integral components of a single continuous circulation that satisfies 2π phase invariance, consistent with Dirac's argument for charge quantization $0, \pm 1$, or $\pm 2e$.

The reactions of these quantized strings concretize electron capture $p^+ + e^- \rightarrow n + \nu_e$. Upon approaching the proton, the electron torus opens and emits a neutrino loop, forming a highly reactive W^- boson. This open string then annihilates with the adjacent up quark. Their constituent quanta pairwise uncoil into the vacuum, entirely eliminating u . The residual arc of W^- becomes a down quark which binds via a gluon to the remaining nucleon structure to form the neutron.

FIG. 8. Left: The electron capture begins near one of the proton up quarks u (red toroidal arc), where the electron (blue torus) opens up and transforms into the W^- boson by emitting one loop quantum, the neutrino. Middle: Subsequently, $2/3$ of W^- annihilates with u into a paired ray of photons (gray waves). Right: The remaining $1/3$ of W^- as a down quark closes the circulation into the neutron. (View as stereo by focusing each eye on a separate structure.)

The nucleon truncated tetrahedron suggests face-to-face packing. In ${}^4_2\text{He}$, two of such tetrahedra, each containing a proton and neutron, are juxtaposed; in ${}^{16}_8\text{O}$, eight; and in ${}^{40}_{20}\text{Ca}$, 20 truncated tetrahedra are packed in a honeycomb (see Colab

or GitHub). This layered array of nearest, next-nearest, next-next-nearest neighbors, and beyond, corresponds to the magic numbers 2, 8, 20, 28, 50, \dots , of enhanced nuclear stability, providing a structural basis for the nuclear shell model.

However, despite being doubly magic, ${}^{24}_8\text{O}$ and ${}^{28}_8\text{O}$ [55, 56] remain unstable because their two-fold neutron and neutron-neutron symmetries break the three-fold proton-neutron symmetry (Fig. 7), optimal for honeycomb packing. Although additional neutrons reduce Coulomb repulsion, their disproportionate scaling with proton number ultimately outweighs the spin-neutral attraction and terminates the magic nuclei series: ${}^4_2\text{He}$, ${}^{16-18}_8\text{O}$, ${}^{40-48}_{20}\text{Ca}$, ${}^{58-64}_{28}\text{Ni}$, ${}^{112-124}_{50}\text{Sn}$, and ${}^{202-208}_{82}\text{Pb}$.

The last stable nucleus, ${}^{208}_{82}\text{Pb}$, is a prolate-like triangular bipyramid with three truncated equatorial vertices, totaling $2 \times 2(\sum_{n=1}^5 n^2 - 3) = 208$ nucleons [57]. In turn, ${}^{176}_{70}\text{Yb}$, with $2 \times 2(\sum_{n=4}^5 (n^2 - 3) + 3^2) = 176$ nucleons, is an oblate-like bipyramid. Notably without invoking a hypothetical fifth-force boson, the non-linearity in the ${}^{168-176}_{70}\text{Yb}$ King plot follows from the nuclear shape shifting between prolate and oblate as neutrons sequentially fill equatorial ($n = 4, 5$) and polar ($n = 1, 2$) vacancies [58, 59]. Similarly, the anomalously large neutron capture cross section of ${}^{88}_{40}\text{Zr}$ [60] is attributed to its multiple equatorial and polar lattice vacancies (see Colab or GitHub). The ordered nuclear lattice also provides a physical basis for the parity violation observed in the Wu experiment ${}^{60}_{27}\text{Co} \rightarrow {}^{60}_{28}\text{Ni} + e^- + \bar{\nu}_e + 2\gamma$. As the decaying neutron is aligned with this compact lattice within the external magnetic field, the electron is emitted in a specific direction rather than isotropically. In this view, the observed asymmetry arises from the aligned nuclear array rather than a fundamental parity violation.

2. Baryon variants

Besides nucleons and other $J = 1/2$ baryons, short-lived $J = 3/2$ resonances can be modeled as quarks toggling between the faces of two tetrahedra situated above and below the gluon plane (Fig. 9). For example, the measured masses $1232 \pm 2 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ of Δ^{++} (uuu), Δ^+ (uud), Δ^0 (udd), and Δ^- (ddd) states align with the weighted average of these *cis* and *trans* configurations: $312.5 + 2 \times (312.5 + 607.9)/2 = 1232.9 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ (Eq. (13)). While Δ^+ and Δ^0 decay into the isospin $J = 1/2$ doublet, p^+ and n , stable configurations merely bifurcating the paired-photon rays of the vacuum, Δ^{++} and Δ^- remain inherently unstable because their fully symmetric $J = 3/2$ quartet trifurcates the vacuum rays, thereby manifesting the Pauli exclusion principle.

FIG. 9. Stereo view of an excited uud mode. (Scale the image for the best 3D perception.)

3. Heavy-flavor baryons

Strange and charm quarks are toroidal arcs with singly-twisted loops, while bottom and top quarks possess doubly-twisted loops. These increasingly curved paths make them more massive than their first-generation counterparts (Fig. 10). Baryons containing these heavy-flavor quarks decay by opening, untwisting, and emitting mesons as required by energy conservation. In this way, the twisting number concretizes the abstract quantum number of flavor.

Particles containing three distinct quarks, such as Ξ_c (usc), exhibit three distinct spin-symmetry configurations. For $J = 1/2$, Ξ_c^+ is an antisymmetric us singlet, whereas Ξ_c^{*+} is a symmetric us triplet. For $J = 3/2$, Ξ_c^{*+} is a fully symmetric usc triplet. These, along with higher-angular-momentum baryon resonances, illustrate the wide variety of triquark configurations.

FIG. 10. Two examples of hyperons with quark compositions udc (left) and uds (right), show in colors: down (blue), up (red), charm (orange), strange (green). Their high masses $m_{udc} = 2452.9$ and $m_{uds} = 1192.6 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ in the $J^P = 1/2^+$ state and 2517.5 and $1383.7 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ in the $J^P = 3/2^+$ state imply that the internal twisting prevents the effective pairwise cancellation of loop curvatures.

C. Mesons

The mesons, comprising quark-antiquark pairs linked by gluons, correspond to two toroidal arcs connected by a quantum of action. These structures form integer-charge combinations $0, \pm 1 e$ to satisfy the 2π phase modularity imposed by the surrounding vacuum. Unlike closed circulations of leptons and baryons, mesonic strings with open ends are inherently transient. Mesons containing heavy-flavor quarks are more curved with singly- or doubly-twisted constituents, rendering them more massive than their first-generation counterparts.

1. Pseudoscalar mesons

In a pseudoscalar meson, the two constituent toroidal arcs lie in a common plane. This configuration generates a field that flips sign under spatial inversion, physically embodying odd parity and spin-0. In accordance with the principle of asymptotic freedom, the arcs revolve freely relative to one another unless the connecting quantum is stretched (Fig. 11).

FIG. 11. Most of π^- (left) and π^+ (right) masses originate from the geodesic curvatures of quanta lacking a counterpart. The complementary structures can form pionium, a short-lived molecule that decays into neutral pions.

During decay $\pi^- \rightarrow \mu^- + \bar{\nu}_\mu$, the toroidal arcs revolve about the gluon and close as μ^- by emitting $\bar{\nu}_\mu$, conserving the stoichiometry $\bar{u}(92) + g(1) + d(46) = \mu(138) + \bar{\nu}_\mu(1)$. Similarly, π^+ decays through W^+ , whereas direct decays to electrons and positrons are suppressed by the specific twist that the W boson acquires from the revolving quarks.

The charged pion $\pi^- (\bar{u}d)$ and $\pi^+ (u\bar{d})$ mass $m_\pi \approx 139.6 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ arises mainly from the two loops that lack counterparts on the opposite sides, $2 \times m_1 = 139.0 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, as the gluon shifts the arcs by π relative to the intact torus (Eq. (13)). In addition, the toroidal pitch contributes by $m_e = 0.5 \text{ MeV}/c^2$.

The neutral pion π^0 is an antisymmetric superposition $(|u\bar{u}\rangle - |d\bar{d}\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$ (Fig. 12). Its two quark-antiquark *trans* configurations pack into a pair of broken-tori, resulting in a mass $m_\pi^0 \approx 135.0 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, slightly lower than that of the π^\pm *cis* configurations. Even so, π^0 self-annihilates its constituents much more rapidly than π^\pm transforms into lepton tori, while other decay modes are greatly suppressed.

In contrast to the isospin triplet π^- , π^+ , π^0 , the singlet σ , the symmetric superposition $(|u\bar{u}\rangle + |d\bar{d}\rangle)/\sqrt{2}$ (Fig. 12), is much heavier, over $500 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ with a notably large width. The vacuum's paired-photon rays curve sharply within the narrow slits of the broken tori, and consequently, the singlet rapidly decays into the triplet states.

FIG. 12. The neutral pion π^0 (left) is an antisymmetric superposition of quark-antiquark pairs, whereas the σ meson (right) is a symmetric superposition. Their large mass difference derives from the small structural difference in the narrow slits that dominates the coupling to the vacuum.

Heavy-flavor quarks are too curved to form mesonic superpositions. Instead, neutral pseudoscalar mesons oscillate $K^0(d\bar{s}) \leftrightarrow \bar{K}^0(\bar{d}s)$ through intermediates $c\bar{u} \leftrightarrow u\bar{c}$ by repeatedly reacting with W^+ and W^- . The string's directional character in flavor changes $\bar{s} + W^+ \rightarrow u$ and $s + W^- \rightarrow \bar{u}$ accounts for the short-lived symmetric superposition's $(K^0 + \bar{K}^0)/\sqrt{2}$ decay into $\pi^+\pi^-$ and $\pi^0\pi^0$ and the long-lived antisymmetric superposition's $(K^0 - \bar{K}^0)/\sqrt{2}$ decay into $\pi^+\pi^-\pi^0$ and its CP-violating decay into $\pi^+\pi^-$. Similarly, the CP violation in the $B^0 \leftrightarrow \bar{B}^0$ oscillations derives from the string's directional flavor asymmetry between d preceding \bar{b} in B^0 and \bar{d} preceding b in \bar{B}^0 . The same argument holds for strong CP violation in the asymmetrical decays of $\Lambda_b^0 \rightarrow pK^-\pi^+\pi^-$ and $\bar{\Lambda}_b^0 \rightarrow \bar{p}K^+\pi^-\pi^+$ [61].

2. Vector mesons

In a vector meson, the two constituent arcs are situated on two faces of a tetrahedron. This configuration generates a vector field that remains invariant under spatial inversion and SU(3) transformations, physically embodying even parity and spin-1. According to Eq. (13), $m_\rho \approx 775.4 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ of ρ^- in $\bar{u}d$ and $d\bar{u}$ states arises from three contributions: i) the loop quanta in the two arcs departing at the increasing angle θ_{ij} , yield $2 \times 312.5 = 625.0 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, ii) the two loop quanta without counterparts contribute $2 \times m_1 = 139.0 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ similar to the planar pion, and iii) a minor correction of $1/2 \times 1/3 \times m_1 = 11.6 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ derives from the phase shift imposed by the tetrahedron's dihedral angle $\phi = \arccos(1/3)$ (Fig. 13).

Unlike the pseudoscalar triplet and singlet, the masses of ρ^- , ρ^+ , ρ^0 , and ω are nearly degenerate, since the broken tori are less restrained in open tetrahedral configurations than in tight planar configurations (Figs. 12 and 13).

3. Exotic particles

A tetraquark is a molecule of two vector mesons, where two quark-antiquark pairs occupy the four tetrahedron faces. For example, the mesonic resonance $Y(4140)$ of $c\bar{c}s\bar{s}$ dissociates into J/ψ and ϕ mesons. In turn, the $P_c^+(4380)$ pentaquark $uudc\bar{c}$ is a baryon combined with a vector meson. Less exotically, the $d^*(2380)$ hexaquark $uu\bar{d}\bar{d}$ resembles the interlaced p^+ and n (Fig. 7) [62]. Similarly to the two-neutron dibaryon, a compact hexaquark configuration $u\bar{d}\bar{d}ud$ may exist in neutron star cores. Under further compression, four down quarks could fuse pairwise into two antiup quarks, resulting in $u\bar{u}u\bar{u}$ (Fig. 14) which packs into a truncated tetrahedral honeycomb [33]. The post-merger gravitational-wave ringdown signal [63] may distinguish such a quantum lattice, effectively a "giant neutron" with a massive magnetic moment, from superfluid models with quantized vortices (see Colab or GitHub).

The $u\bar{u}u\bar{u}$ and $d\bar{d}d\bar{d}$ tetraquarks can combine into an octaquark string that spans all four faces of a tetrahedron (Fig. 14). Similarly to W and Z (Figs. 5 and 6), its doubly broken tori with narrow slits couple tightly to the vacuum's paired-photon rays. This self-conjugate high-symmetry structure, characterized by high mass, spin-0, and even parity, shares the properties of the Higgs boson ($m_H = 125.35 \text{ GeV}/c^2$), naturally accounting for its decay channels into heavy quarks, leptons, gauge bosons, or photon pairs.

In this view, the ephemeral Higgs particle manifests the topological packing limit of quanta within a single tetrahedral unit, rather than serving as a mechanism for mass generation. Accordingly, it is not a hypothetical Higgs field that limits the range of the weak nuclear force, but the paired-photon vacuum itself by coupling strongly to the open tori of W and Z (Figs. 5 and 6).

FIG. 13. The isospin triplet of the charged ρ^- (above left) and ρ^+ (above right) and the neutral ρ^0 meson (below left) and the isospin singlet ω (below right).

FIG. 14. Four-quark $u\bar{u}u\bar{u}$ circulation viewed along the edge-to-edge common perpendicular of the tetrahedron (left). Extending to $d\bar{d}d\bar{d}$, the eight-arc string closes into a highly symmetrical octaquark, its own antiparticle, with properties similar to those of the Higgs particle (right).

IV. DISCUSSION

The strict stoichiometry observed in the transformations interconnecting all elementary particles and the vacuum suggests that they share a single basic building block. By identifying the quantum of action $h = Et$ as this fundamental unit, particles are understood as strings of quanta whose geometric characteristics—curvature, winding number, and curl—determine their physical properties: energy E and period t , as well as mass m , charge q , and magnetic moment μ . The resulting variations in the density and phase of the surrounding paired-photon vacuum manifest themselves as gravitational and electromagnetic fields. In this way, tangible strings of quanta render particles and their interactions comprehensible, much as atomic models once rendered molecules and their reactions intelligible.

Given that all complexity ultimately builds up from these discrete quanta, their statistical behavior is evident across scales and scopes, extending far beyond Planck’s radiation law. Skewed, near-lognormal distributions that accumulate sigmoidally and thus follow power laws, often over several orders of magnitude, are ubiquitous [64, 65]. Multiplicative processes in particle production, jet fragmentation, and heavy nuclei collisions also produce skewed distributions with cumulative power-law characteristics [66–68]. The statistical physics of open quantized systems shows that these universal patterns emerge from the least-time evolution toward thermodynamic balance, from nuclear reactions to the distribution of galaxies and voids [69, 70], from chemical reactions to the evolution of species [71, 72].

Particularly pertinent to particle physics is that natural processes converge on standards to attain free energy minima. Accordingly, the discrete set of elementary particles parallels the canonical set of biological molecules, just as the handedness of particles mirrors the homochirality of biomolecules [73]. The handedness standard known as matter emerged—just as its mirror-image, antimatter, could have—for the universe to evolve toward thermodynamic balance. The standard constituents form stable particles, which in turn form functional structures, such as stars, supernovae, black holes, where the quanta of matter convert into the quanta that jet out as spatial substance [32, 33, 74]. Immersed in this undulating quantized vacuum, any particle string must satisfy 2π periodicity. This topological closure inherently enforces the vacuum angle $\theta_{QCD} \equiv 0$, resolving the strong CP problem and rendering the axion field superfluous.

Rather than starting off with an “excess” of matter over antimatter arising from speculative intrinsic differences or the strong CP violation, all matter remains net neutral by comprising equal amounts of oppositely handed constituents, which annihilate into the substance of space on the path to heat death. As the energy density tends toward zero and the wave speed toward infinity, the basic building block—the quantum of action h —remains invariant. From this unifying perspective, the hierarchy of forces arises from the sheer scale of structures: the strong force is so strong because the energy density is so high within minute particles; gravity is so weak because the energy density is so low within immense voids.

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